

MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES

Jyoti Deshmukh¹, D.D. Suradkar² and M.M. Bhogoankar³

College of Agriculture, Latur,

V.N.M. KV Parbhani, Maharashtra, India..

MS Received: 16.11.2024; MS Revised:29.12.2024; MS Accepted:30.12.2024)

MS 3347

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRIBUSINESS MANAGEMENT)

Abstract

The present study determines the motivational factors responsible for agricultural enterprises. A sample of 120 agricultural students were interviewed from the three selected constituent colleges of agriculture i.e. College of Agriculture Latur, College of Agriculture Osmanabad, College of Agriculture Ambajogai for the proper study which comes under, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani. The findings revealed that, the motivational factors which are ranked according to preference given by the agricultural students to them. Majority (95.83%) of the agricultural students were motivated to start their own agricultural enterprise as an "to prove capacity/ability", "government help" 92.50 per cent, "for better standard of living" 91.66 per cent, "to inspire by competition" 90.00 per cent, "to develop social status" 86.66 per cent, "to prove innovation is economically benefited" 85.00 per cent, "to earn more money" 80.83 per cent, "to inspire by co-operative feelings" 76.66 per cent, "to show independent decision power" 75.00 per cent, and "to satisfy ego" 52.50 per cent.

Keywords – Motivational factors, agricultural enterprises.

Introduction

Agriculture plays vital role in Indian economy. We can make it possible through development and utilization of specially trained man power of our agricultural graduate. Entrepreneurship is the most important thing to day life. Any innovation was carried out through entrepreneur because he is the person one who take risks, opportunities to generate viable profit. He also innovator and ability to take lead a group of people. The entrepreneurship is the booming during the last two decades and has assumed new dimensions with respect to its different disciplines.

The prosperity and progress of nation depends on the entrepreneurial quality of its people. If they are enterprising, ambitious and courageous enough to bear entrepreneurial risk, the community/society will develop quickly. Such people are identified as entrepreneurs and their character reflects in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial potential can be found and developed anywhere irrespective of age, qualification, experience or socio-economic background. Entrepreneurs are people who realize new opportunities and channelize effort in the proper direction.

There is a tremendous scope for empowerment of agricultural graduates through establishment of Dairy, Poultry, Fishery, Goat rearing, Floriculture, Sericulture, Mushroom cultivation, Kitchen gardening, Food Processing and Value Addition, Green house, Poly house enterprises etc; and thus they can even become employment generator. But many a time it has been reported that only few students want to become entrepreneurs. This emphasizes the need of creating an aptitude among the students for taking up entrepreneurship which will enable them to become employment providers rather than employment seekers. Recent experiences indicate that the economic progress of few countries, particularly developed countries is due to the contribution of large number of small entrepreneurs employing up in their establishment. So, large numbers of such entrepreneurs for

developing and transforming village clusters into sustainable economic units needed (Kalam, A.P.J. 2007).

To develop entrepreneurship is a serious and inevitable factor in countries and it is necessary in the difficult conditions in our community. Entrepreneurs, certainly thanks to their characteristics are capable for developing and providing resources like land, capital, raw materials and human resources. Today, entrepreneurs have the benefit like, job creation improving quality of life, proper distribution of income, social issue support, the creation of a welfare which are important factors in the development and wellbeing of nations. Increasing unemployment particularly among the educated will act as alarm of danger for governors of countries and therefore it is necessary to solve this problem for which careful, comprehensive and long term planning is required. Entrepreneurship is one way that deserves a permanent move for employment should be prioritized. Hence especially young people must be trained in order to have ability for creating job opportunities and self-acceptance with the flexibility of complex, unsecure new jobs in the labour market and able to make good with innovations and risk (Sarasiab *et al.*, 2013).

Methodology

The present study was conducted mainly with the objective to study Entrepreneurial attitude of agricultural students. For the study three constituent colleges of agriculture i.e college of agriculture Latur, college of agriculture Osmanabad, college of agriculture Ambajogai which comes under Pabhani university. Total 120 respondents were selected for the present study. From each college, forty students who were studying in VIII th semester were selected randomly for the study. Ex-post-facto research design was used for the study. Data was coded, tabulated, analysed and interpreted using suitable statistical parameters

Results and discussion**I. Socio-demographic profile of the respondents**

Table: 1 distribution of the respondents according to Profile characteristics of Agricultural students (N=120)

Sr. No.	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Birth order		
	1 st born children	32	26.67
	2 nd born children	52	43.33
	3 rd born children	24	20.00
2.	Family background		
	Rural	88	73.33
	Urban	32	26.67
	3.	Academic achievement	
First class with distinction (above 8.4)		19	15.83
First class (7.5 to 8.4)		52	43.33
Second class (7.0 to 7.4)		41	34.17
4.	Participation in extracurricular activities		
	Pass class (6.5 to 6.9)	8	06.67

	Low participation (up to 15)	27	25.00
	Medium participation (between 16 to 18)	63	52.50
	High participation (above 18)	30	22.50
5.	Size of family		
	Small (up to 3 member)	5	04.17
	Medium (between 4 to 6 member)	104	86.67
	Large (above 6 member)	11	09.16
6.	Father's education		
	Illiterate	7	05.83
	Literate (Can read and Write)	5	04.17
	Primary school level	17	14.17
	High school level	18	15.00
	Higher secondary school level	23	19.17
	Graduate	34	28.33
	Graduate and above graduate	16	13.33
7.	Father's occupation		
	Labour	8	06.67
	Govt. Service	23	19.16
	Business	13	10.83
	Independent profession	8	06.67
	Agricultural farming	57	47.50
	Private service	11	09.17
8.	Family land holding		
	Marginal (Up to 1.00 ha)	25	20.83
	Small (1.01 to 2.00 ha)	35	29.17
	Semi medium (2.1 to 4.00 ha)	10	08.33
	Medium (4.1 to 10.00 ha)	44	36.67
	Large (above 10 ha)	1	00.83
	Landless	5	04.17
9.	Family income		
	Low (up to Rs. 64,061)	3	2.50
	Medium (between Rs. 64,062 to 90,056)	12	10.00
	High (above 90,056)	105	87.50
10.	Achievement motivation		
	Low (up to 19)	21	17.50
	Medium (between 20 to 22)	92	76.67
	High (above 22)	7	05.83
11.	Innovativeness		
	Low (up to 12)	26	21.67
	Medium (between 13 to 17)	79	65.83
	High (above 17)	15	12.50
12.	Market orientation		
	Low (up to 12)	23	19.17
	Medium (between 13 to 16)	85	70.83
	High (above 16)	12	10.00
13.	Decision making ability		
	Low (up to 24)	21	17.50
	Medium (between 25 to 28)	76	63.33
	High (above 28)	23	19.17

A number of profile characteristics were selected as independent variables to find out profile of agricultural students of the study area. The number of profile characteristics as independent variables to find out profile of farmers of the study area. The results obtained from the above table that more than two fifth (43.33%) of the students were second born children 26.67 per cent of the students born at first position followed by 20.00 per cent of students born at third position and number of students born at fourth and above position were 10.00 per cent. Family background wise composition of the study sample reveals that majority (73.33%) of the graduating students were from rural areas and 26.67 per cent students were from urban background. As regards academic achievement more than two fifth (43.33%) of the students were from first class category. Whereas agricultural students who got

second class, First class with distinction, and pass class were 34.17, 15.83, and 06.67 per cent, respectively. As regards participation in extracurricular activities more than half (52.50%) of the students had medium participation in extracurricular activities followed by 25.00 per cent students were having low participation in extracurricular activities and 22.50 per cent students had high participation in extracurricular activities. Size of family wise composition of the study sample reveals that majority (86.67%) of the graduating students were from medium size family, 09.16 per cent of the students from large size and 04.17 per cent of the students were having small size families. As regards father's education more than one fourth (28.33%) of the student's father were graduates, followed by the students father who had higher secondary school education were 19.17

per cent, high school level 15.00 per cent, primary school level 14.17 per cent, graduate and above graduate 13.33 per cent, illiterate 05.83 per cent and 04.17 per cent were literate. It is revealed from above table that slightly less than half (47.50%) of the student's father were engaged in agricultural farming, followed by 19.16 per cent student's father were engaged in government service, 10.83 per cent were engaged in business. The student's father was engaged in private service and independent professions were 09.17 and 06.67 per cent, respectively. Only 06.67 per cent student's father was worked as labour. As regards family land holding more than one third (36.67%) of the agricultural students were having medium size of family land holding, followed by 29.17, 20.83, 08.33, per cent of the students were having small, marginal, semi medium size of family land holding respectively, 04.17 per cent of students were landless and only 00.83 per cent of the students were having large size of family land holding. Family income wise composition of the study sample reveals that more than one fourth (87.50%) of the agricultural student's had high family income, followed by 10.00 per cent of the student's were having medium family income and 2.50 per cent of the student's had low family income. As regards achievement motivation more than three

fourth (76.67%) of the agricultural students were belonged to medium achievement motivation category, followed by 17.50 per cent of the agricultural students had low achievement motivation and 05.83 per cent of the respondents had high achievement motivation. As regards innovativeness slightly less than two third (65.83%) of the agricultural student's had medium level of innovativeness, followed by 21.67 per cent of the agricultural students were having low level of innovativeness and 12.50 per cent of the agricultural student's had high level of innovativeness. Market orientation wise composition of the study sample reveals that more than two third (70.83%) of the agricultural students had medium level of market orientation; while 19.17 per cent of the agricultural students had low level of market orientation and 10.00 per cent of the agricultural students had high level of market orientation. As regards decision making ability majority (63.33%) of the agricultural students had medium level of decision making ability followed by, 19.17 per cent of the agricultural students had high level of decision making ability and 17.50 per cent of the agricultural students had low level of decision making ability.

II. Factors responsible for agricultural entrepreneurial enterprises

Table 2: Distribution of the agricultural students according to their factors responsible for entrepreneurial enterprises

N=120

Sr. No.	Motivational factors	Frequency	Per cent	Rank
1	To prove innovation is economically benefited.	102	85.00	VI
2	To prove capacity/ability	115	95.83	I
3	To satisfy ego	63	52.50	X
4	To develop social status	104	86.66	V
5	For better standard of living	110	91.66	III
6	To earn more money	97	80.83	VII
7	To inspire by co-operative feelings	92	76.66	VIII
8	To show independent decision power	90	75.00	IX
9	Government help	111	92.50	II
10	To inspire by competition	108	90.00	IV

Above table indicated that, the motivational factors which are ranked according to preference given by the agricultural students to them. It is seen from the above table that majority (95.83%) of the agricultural students were motivated to start their own agricultural enterprise as an "to prove capacity/ability", "government help" 92.50 per cent, "for better standard of living" 91.66 per cent, "to inspire by competition" 90.00 per cent, "to develop social status" 86.66 per cent, "to prove innovation is economically benefited" 85.00 per cent, "to earn more money" 80.83 per cent, "to inspire by co-operative feelings" 76.66 per cent, "to show independent decision power" 75.00 per cent, and "to satisfy ego" 52.50 per cent.

References

1. **Abdulah, A. A. and Sulaiman, N. N. (2013).** Factors that influence the interest of youth agricultural entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(3): 288-302.
2. **Ajit, C. (2004).** Determination of attitude, occupational aspiration and preference for placement of

B. Sc. Agriculture students of Gujarat state. *M. Sc. (Agri.) Thesis (Unpub.)*, G.A.U., Anand.

3. **Deshmukh, P. R. and Kadam, R. P. (2012).** Attitude of agricultural students towards entrepreneurship, *AGRESCO report* submitted to social sciences Sub Committee. College of Agriculture, VNMKV, Parbhani.
4. **Lawrence, C. and Ganguli, D. (2012).** Entrepreneurial behaviour of dairy farmers in Tamil Nadu. *Indian Research Journal Extension Education*, 12(1), Jan 2012.
5. **Sajjan, S.P. (2006).** A comparative profile analysis of the rural youth in the irrigated and rainfed tracts of Bagalkot district <http://etd.usad.edu/t/8691>.
6. **Saranya M. N. (2015).** Attitude of agricultural graduating students towards entrepreneurship. *M. Sc. (Agri.) Thesis (Unpub.)*, VNMKV, Parbhani.
7. **Waman, G.K., Girase, K.A. and Desai B.R. (2000).** Aspirations and employment of agricultural graduates. *Maharashtra Journal of Extension Education*. 19:141-144.